

Adoption of the ORCID identifier by European Research Council grantees hosted in Spain

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This study analyses ORCID iD adoption among researchers with a Spanish host institution who received a European Research Council (ERC) grant in 2014-2020. We study the use of ORCID iD among the researchers and different characteristics of their ORCID records, that is: record completion, record dynamics (date of creation and last updating date) and main updating path. All ERC grantees have an ORCID-iD and an associated profile, which is generally public. On average, each profile contains information in 4 sections, being the work section the one most frequently completed. Fifty percent of the profiles were updated in the last month, increasing the updating rate from Social Sciences & Humanities, to Physical Sciences & Engineering and Life Sciences. Commercial entities were the most frequent source of work update (61%). The degree of adoption of the identifier will be influenced by the policies of institutions, agencies and publishers. However, factors such as the training of researchers and the development of user-friendly tools for profile creation and maintenance are also required.

1. Introduction

Persistent identifiers for researchers are essential to reliably identify authors and their scholarly output, which is important for research institutions, funding agencies, publishers, and researchers themselves. According to an OECD survey, ORCID iD is the author identifier most used by researchers (Bello & Galindo-Rueda, 2020). ORCID iD, which stands for “Open Researcher and Contributor ID” (info.orcid.org/), is a 16-digit identifier launched in 2012 and currently used by millions of researchers worldwide. It has a universal character, as it is supported by a global, not-for-profit organization and it is not tied to specific databases. It provides researchers with a unique, persistent identifier and an ORCID record -a digital CV-, fostering connections among authors, publishers, funders, and other academic publishing stakeholders (ORCID, 2023).

A number of studies analyse the degree of ORCID iD adoption by different communities, such as countries (Youtie et al., 2017; Porter, 2022), regions (Heusse & Cabanac, 2022), or institutions (Boudry & Durand-Barthez, 2020). The ORCID iD adoption rate is stronger in Europe and weaker in Asia and the United States (Youtie et al., 2017). Varied rates of ORCID iD adoption have been described for French university researchers (55%) (Heusse & Cabanac, 2022), for a Portuguese university (90%) (Fernández-Marcial, González-Solar & Vale, 2023) and for corresponding authors surveyed by OECD (60%) (Bello & Galindo-Rueda, 2020).

However, it is not only interesting to know what proportion of researchers have an ORCID iD. It is also important to know whether they have a complete ORCID record and their commitment to updating it, which are issues less frequently studied (Wang et al., 2024), in order to ensure the validity and reliability of ORCID-based studies.

This study focuses on European Research Council (ERC) grant recipients with a Spanish host institution, which is a population of leading researchers, with a high adoption of ORCID iDs (Bordons, Moreno-Solano and González-Albo, 2024), to study the completion and dynamics of their ORCID records and the main updating paths used. The selection of this population of researchers will enable us to differentiate researchers at various career stages, and to explore potential variations by subject area, since grants are grouped by the EC in three domains.

2. Objectives

This work aims to delve into the study of ORCID iD adoption among ERC grant recipients with a Spanish host institution focusing on different aspects:

- Completion of ORCID records, through the study of the information contained in the record sections and in other fields.
- Dynamics of the ORCID records, through the analysis of the date of creation and last update of the records.
- Source of work updating, which may influence the completeness and reliability of the updated data.

In this sense, we have tried to answer the following questions:

- Do all ERC grantees have an ORCID iD and an associated ORCID record?
- Are the different sections of the ORCID record completed?
- Have the records been updated recently?
- Are there differences in ORCID adoption by scientific domain or researcher seniority?
- What are the sources for updating the ORCID profiles?

3. Methods

The list of researchers with a Spanish host institution who received an ERC grant in 2014-2020 was extracted from CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/projects/es>). Three funding schemes were considered: Starting grants (STG), that are aimed for talented early-career scientists; Consolidator grants (COG), for scientists who want to consolidate their career and establish a research team; and Advanced grants (ADG), for leading IPs who want long-term funding for ambitious projects. Grants are grouped by the ERC into three domains: Life Sciences (LS), Physical Sciences and Engineering (PE), and Social Sciences and Humanities (SH).

The ORCID iDs of the researchers were obtained by querying the ORCID website (<https://orcid.org>) with the first name and last name of the researchers. Some difficulties were encountered in identifying the ORCID iD of researchers, such as very common names, researchers with more than one profile, incomplete names in the profiles, or even names not available ('Name is private'). In these cases, other sources on the web were consulted to identify the correct ORCID iD of the author, considering also the researcher's institution and thematic field.

Once the list of ORCID iDs was compiled, the ORCID API was queried by a script written in Python in order to obtain the ORCID records. The final data were downloaded in July 2024.

The following aspects of the ORCID records were studied:

1. Completion of ORCID records

Each researcher's ORCID record was examined to determine whether it was public or private and how fully it had been completed. We assessed whether the records included information in the following sections available through the ORCID API: biography, employment, education and qualification, funding, works and peer review (for a detailed description of section content, see <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/sections/360002501973-ORCID-Metadata>). In addition, the presence of other relevant data is analyzed: country, email, keywords, scientific URL – labelled as 'Websites & social links' – and external identifiers – 'Other IDs' –.

2. Dynamics of ORCID records

For each record, we obtained the date of its creation and the date of its most recent update (year, month, day). The number of months since the record was created and last modified were obtained for every record. We obtained information on the number of validated and self-asserted works. Validated items are those added by a trusted ORCID member organization (e.g. a publisher, funder or research institution). Self-asserted items are those that have been manually added directly by the record owner.

3. Sources of work updating

For each item included in the work section of the ORCID records, different fields are downloaded such as: title, publication type, document identifiers (doi, handle, ISBN, eid, etc.), publication year and source. The "source" field collects information about who is adding the item to the record: the researcher, a system approved by the researcher or a trusted institution.

It should be noted that sometimes a given item may have been added in the ORCID record by more than one source, but the system groups them together to avoid them being considered as two different items, that is, they are considered as versions of a specific item. However, for the study of sources, we have considered all of them.

4. Results

From 2014 to 2020, 357 ERC grants were awarded to researchers with a Spanish host institution, averaging 51 grants per year. Half of the grants fall into the category of PE, followed by LS (27%) and SH (23%). The population is strongly masculinized (72% of men vs 28% of women), especially in the ADG category (85% men vs. 15% women). Starting grants were the most frequent (39%), followed by consolidator grants (37%), and advanced grants (24%). The distribution of researchers by funding scheme was quite similar in the three domains. However, STG researchers represent a higher percentage in SH than in the other two domains (46%).

Most of the records were directly created by the users, while very few (5%) were created on behalf of the researchers by their institutions.

4.1. ORCID record completion

All the ERC researchers have ORCID iDs, and around 98% (N=351) display a public profile. Profiles contain information in an average of four sections. Only 4% of the profiles contain information in all eight sections, while 8% show information in just one section. Most profiles

(95%) provide information about works (publications and other output types), and in the rest (5%) works are not included or belong to authors with private profiles. This proportion is quite similar in all three domains. Employment data is also included very often (78%). On the contrary, few researchers have completed the biography section: around 31% on average, although this percentage is somewhat higher in SH. Over half (around 60%) provide data about academic background or qualifications and peer-review activity. Funding data are included in 45% of the profiles, but it is higher in SH (63%) than in the other two domains.

Figure 1. Completion of sections in the ORCID profiles

Profiles also contain information about other interesting aspects which do not have their own section. At least one external identifier (Researcher iD, Scopus iD, etc.) is provided by around 90% of researchers in the different domains. Researchers in SH are more likely to display their websites and social links (70% of the profiles), while it is present only in around 50% of the profiles in LS and PE. The information provided in this section is very varied: it may include the personal, project or research group webpage; the research center website; research portal; Google Scholar Profiles; Wikipedia pages or other social networks pages like LinkedIn; ResearchGate or Facebook. Keywords that describe the research line of researchers are included in around 40% of the profiles. Finally, the country is shown in about half of the records and only 10% of the researchers provide their email address.

4.2. ORCID record dynamics

We studied when the profiles were created and how fast they were updated. Around 50% of ORCID records were created ten years ago or before, with a range between four and twelve years (no differences by domain or funding scheme were observed). Fifty percent of profiles were updated in the last month. Interestingly, the profiles were faster updated in LS and PE than in SH. Half of the records had been updated in the last two weeks in LS, in the last 3 weeks in PE and in the last 3 months in SH.

4.3. Sources of work updating

The sources of work update can be grouped into several types: commercial entities (61%), non-profit organizations (15%), researchers (10%), repositories (7%) and research institutions (6%). Elsevier and Clarivate stand out among the commercial sources, while CrossRef is the most prominent among the non-profit ones and PubMed predominates among the repositories.

5. Discussion and conclusions

ORCID iD adoption among the ERC researchers analysed in this study is very high: all the researchers have an ORCID iD, and most of them have public profiles. This adoption rate is higher than described in the literature (Youtie et al. 2017; Heusse & Cabanac, 2022; Porter, 2022), which means that ERC grantees are more committed to the identifier than the average scientist, probably because the use of ORCID is recommended by the European Commission (2017). However, the completion of the ORCID records is variable. Almost all profiles include data on works, while funding and biography are completed less frequently. Thus, there is still room for improvement.

Overall, a quite rapid updating of the ORCID profiles is observed. This is facilitated by the existence of automatic update possibilities, implemented mainly in the work section. A slower update is observed in SH, probably due to the lower productivity of researchers in this domain, which reduces the frequency with which updates of output information are required.

In order to facilitate the successful implementation of ORCID in the scientific community it would be important that researchers be aware of the benefits of having a profile, so that they are committed to completing it. Thus, the training of researchers on ORCID advantages and profile management and the development of more user-friendly tools in the creation and maintenance of the profiles are crucial factors in facilitating implementation.

Studies on the level of adoption of ORCID iD and the barriers limiting its use in the scientific community are essential to assist in the successful implementation of the identifier. Moreover, improving completion and quality of ORCID records will contribute to enhance the reliability of research based on ORCID profile data.

6. References

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Open science practices

The data that support the findings of this study will be openly available in DIGITAL-CSIC.

Author contributions

M.B is in charge of the **conceptualization** of the research, L.M-S. & B.G-A are responsible of the **data curation**. All the authors have participated in the development of the **methodology**, **investigation** and **formal analysis**. **Writing – original draft** has been made by M.B. and **writing – review & editing** by M.B., L.M-S & B.G-A.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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